

Towards Unsupervised Incremental and Proportional Myocontrol based on Higher-Density Surface Electromyography

Alisa Schulz¹, Fabio Egle¹, Marius Osswald², Alessandro Del Vecchio² and Claudio Castellini^{1,3}

Abstract—Upper limb differences present tremendous challenges for autonomy in daily living, and current prostheses often face high abandonment rates due to complexity and lack of functionality. This study investigates fully unsupervised incremental myocontrol using higher-density surface EMG. Utilizing incremental sparse non-negative matrix factorization (ISNMF), we employed two 32-channel sEMG bracelets to incrementally extract muscle synergies from EMG signals in real-time. Eight able-bodied participants underwent this unsupervised training paradigm with an increasing number of target synergies and were evaluated with a virtual target achievement control (TAC) test. Participants demonstrated up to six independently controllable synergies in full-intensity tasks, exceeding the current state of the art. However, proportional control remained challenging, reflected in a median success rate of 10% for half-intensity targets. Subjective feedback across the number of synergies showed only small variations in cognitive and physical workload despite increased complexity. This approach shows promise for enabling fully unsupervised myocontrol, but further refinement of training protocol and hyperparameters, as well as testing on users with limb differences, are necessary to validate and improve this approach.

I. INTRODUCTION

Congenital anomalies of the upper limb affect approximately one in 500 births [1]. Italy and the UK report 3500 and 5200 upper limb amputations per year, respectively [2]. Furthermore, due to an aging population and increasing prevalence of diabetes and cardiovascular disease, the number of people with upper limb amputation in the US is expected to double by 2050 [3]. Individuals with limb difference (LD) face challenges in autonomy and daily functioning as well as a heightened risk to their psychological well-being, including anxiety and depression [4].

Despite the considerable advances in the field of upper limb prosthesis (ULP) in the last decades, prosthesis abandonment is still very high [5]. The reasons for this include comfort, lack of functionality, and complex control systems [6]. Methods based on pattern recognition (PR) have been developed in the last decades to approach the latter two reasons [7], [8]. One of the main issues with the developed

prosthesis control methods is the non-stationarity of surface electromyography (sEMG) signals due to sweat, muscle fatigue, sensor shift, and user adaptation [9]. To overcome this problem and to foster the co-adaptation process between the user and system, incremental learning approaches providing regression or classification have been developed and tested in recent years [10]–[12]. While these methods empower the user to voluntarily update their model, they are still limited by the requirement for the user to provide accurate labels. These labels can be provided either by a contralateral data acquisition [13], by following a visual reference [14], or by training on a steady-state, e.g., a certain percentage of the maximum contraction. Providing these labels can be especially challenging for people with LD, as this requires dedicated pre-prosthetic user training and data acquisition protocols [15]. Unsupervised myocontrol (UM) allows continuous adaptation without labels, thus potentially solving this problem. Furthermore, instead of only using small portions of labeled data, it allows a stream of (interaction) data to update the model continuously.

In 2009, Jiang et al. [16] applied the non-negative matrix factorization (NMF) as a myocontrol algorithm to achieve both proportional and simultaneous control of multiple degrees of freedom (DOFs). Building on this, Lin et al. proposed a NMF algorithm with additional sparsity constraints for the control signal, thereby simplifying the training and even allowing arbitrary movements during the training phase [17]. Yeung et al. [18] designed an incremental NMF that can adapt to changes and counteract performance degradation. Gigli et al. [19] developed this approach further by adding an arbitrary motor mapping, which eliminates the necessity for labeled data. Finally, [20] adapted the method to add muscle synergies progressively during the training process.

This work investigates the feasibility and potential of combining incremental unsupervised learning with higher-density sEMG as previously used in such unsupervised myocontrol paradigms. For this, we implemented the incremental sparse NMF (ISNMF) approach described by Gigli et al. [19] in combination with two 32-channel sEMG dry electrode bracelets. Although sEMG setups with higher number of electrodes, in many cases high-density (interelectrode distance ≤ 10 mm) electrode grids have previously been used for real-time myocontrol in experimental conditions [14], [21]–[23], most of these works rely either on supervised approaches, the use of computationally demanding neural networks, adhesive electrode grids applied to the skin with conductive paste limiting their usefulness in real-world settings, or a combination of the above.

*This work was partially supported by the European Commission’s Horizon Europe Framework Program with the project IntelliMan (AI-Powered Manipulation System for Advanced Robotic Service, Manufacturing and Prosthetics) under Grant Agreement 101070136.

¹Assistive Intelligent Robotics Lab, Department Artificial Intelligence in Biomedical Engineering, Friedrich-Alexander Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91052 Erlangen, Germany

²n-squared Lab, Department Artificial Intelligence in Biomedical Engineering, Friedrich-Alexander Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91052 Erlangen, Germany

³Institute of Robotics and Mechatronics, German Aerospace Center, 82234 Wessling, Germany

Fig. 1. *Experimental setup of the online myocontrol experiment.* Two 32-channel dry electrode bracelets were placed around the participant’s forearm. Each electrode bracelet consisted of two rows of 16 electrodes. The bipolar configuration of the monopolar signals was derived for each pair of electrodes in the longitudinal direction of the arm, resulting in an output of 16 EMG signals per bracelet. Interelectrode distance in the transversal and longitudinal direction is shown in the bottom panel. Signals were preprocessed (see Methods) and then simultaneously fed into a buffer and the latest prediction NMF model. The collected data in the buffer was used to update the currently extracted weights W at defined intervals k_u . The model’s prediction controlled a virtual hand on a monitor, that gave the user feedback on the model’s current prediction.

We tested our developed system in an online myocontrol experiment with eight able-bodied (AB) participants. During the experimental sessions, the subjects had to train a number of muscle synergies incrementally, increasing the number of synergies by one each round. After each round, the participants performed a target achievement control (TAC) test as an objective and filled in the NASA-TLX questionnaire as a subjective measure of perceived workload. To the author’s knowledge, no dry electrode setup with such an electrode density as used in this work has been used for fully unsupervised and incremental online myocontrol to this date.

II. METHODS

A. Processing and Incremental Unsupervised Myocontrol

In order to extract the participants’ movement intention from their sEMG signals, the ISNMF algorithm proposed by Gigli et al. [19] was implemented. The standard NMF algorithm aims to minimize the difference between the input EMG $V \in \mathbb{R}_+^{s \times n}$ consisting of s n -dimensional samples and WH . Where $W \in \mathbb{R}_+^{r \times n}$ contains r extracted synergies and $H \in \mathbb{R}_+^{r \times s}$ holds the activation coefficients. The ISNMF model uses iterative multiplicative updates on input batches of V based on Formula 1 and 2 to extract and refine muscle synergies in the m -th update. The matrices A and B are history matrices and eliminate the necessity of storing the entire training data set. While the forgetting factor μ reduces the contribution of the previous training batches. [19].

$$W^m \leftarrow W^m \circ \frac{\mu A^{m-1} + V_m H_m^{mT}}{\mu W^m B^{m-1} + W^m H_m^m H_m^{mT} + \frac{\mu(1-\mu^m)}{(1-\mu)} \beta W^m} \quad (1)$$

To compute the activation coefficients, H is optimized based on Formula 2.

$$H_m^m \leftarrow H_m^m \circ \frac{W^{mT} V_m}{W^{mT} W^m H_m^m + \gamma (H_m^m)^{-0.5}} \quad (2)$$

To improve the sparsity of the predictions, H is regularised with an $L_{0.5}$ norm weighted by γ , while W is regularised with an L_2 norm weighted by β .

For the online application, two ISNMF models were run in parallel, one for computing the predictions and one performing the updates, to guarantee that predictions were computed in real-time without disruptions through model updates, as shown in Figure 1. Each muscle synergy in W is arbitrarily mapped to a predefined myocontrol action of the hand model. The activation coefficients are normalized to a range of [0, 1] based on the historical 95th percentile of previous activations [19].

B. Hardware

For sEMG acquisition, two 32-channel sEMG bracelets (HD20MM1602B, OT Bioelettronica, Turin, Italy) were placed around the forearm of the participants. The electrodes of the sEMG bracelets are arranged in two columns of 16 electrodes each, with a longitudinal interelectrode distance (IED) of 20 mm between the columns and 13-18.5 mm IED in transversal direction, depending on the participants’ forearm circumference (20.8 - 29.5 cm in this study) (Fig. 1). Signals were sampled at 2000 Hz by a commercially available, wireless amplification system (MUOVI, OT Bioelettronica, Turin, Italy).

C. sEMG Preprocessing

To improve signal stability, the bipolar derivation of each pair of electrodes in the longitudinal direction of the arm was computed and used for further processing, resulting in 16 sEMG signals per bracelet. Then, the EMG was amplified by a factor of 100 and filtered with a bandpass filter over a frequency range of 20 Hz to 90 Hz and a bandstop filter over a frequency range of 45 Hz to 55 Hz. Finally, the root mean square (RMS) was calculated over a sliding window of 500 ms with a step size of 50 ms.

D. Online Myocontrol Experiment

1) *Participants*: The study was conducted with eight AB subjects (sex: 2f, 6m; age: 26.6 ± 3.0 , range [20,30]). Participants 1 and 5 had prior experience in myocontrol-based study designs.

2) *Experimental Setup*: As visualized in Figure 1, two sEMG bracelets, as described in II-B, were placed around the participants' forearm, targeting all superficial extrinsic hand and wrist muscles. The recorded sEMG was preprocessed as described in II-C. Due to limited space available, the wrist, hand, and fingers were not fixed with an orthosis. The participants were placed in front of a monitor that displayed a target hand, and the control hand. The target hand displayed the desired hand postures during the TAC test. While the control hand performed the hand movements according to the currently detected synergy activation and arbitrary motor mapping.

3) *ISNMF*: The value of the forget factor μ , was fixed at 0.9 throughout the course of the online trials. The tolerance ϵ was set to 10^{-5} , and the maximum number of iterations per update and prediction was limited to 200. In each trial, the number of extracted synergies, r , was increased from the initial value of $r = 3$ to a maximum of $r = 7$. The training batch size k_u was set to 10s for $r = [3,4]$, 15s for $r = [5,6]$, and 20s for $r = 7$. The initial values of the regularization terms β and γ were set to 10, although these could be modified by the experimenter if, for example, extracted synergies diminished repeatedly.

4) *Study protocol*: Each participant trains multiple ISNMF models with an increasing number of synergies, starting with three synergies. Each model is trained for a maximum time of ten minutes. Afterward, the ISNMF model was no longer updated, and a TAC test was performed, which requested the participant to reach a specific target position and hold them for 2 seconds with a maximal myocontrol error of 0.2. Thereby the myocontrol error is defined as the maximum component of the elementwise absolute difference between the target and the predicted pose [20]. The target poses require the activation of single synergies at *half-* and *full-intensity* to assess proportional control. Between the training and test phases of the models controlling more than three synergies, the NASA-TLX questionnaire (p. 1) is filled out by the participant. If a new synergy (four or later) could not be correctly activated at all, the experiment was terminated. The study was conducted following the WMA Declaration of Helsinki, participants provided informed consent, and the

experiment was approved by the Ethics Committee of FAU Erlangen-Nürnberg (No. 22-275-S) before the experiments were carried out.

5) *Data Analysis*: The objective evaluation of the myocontrol of the participants was conducted through the analysis of the TAC test results, i.e. the success rate and task completion time. Each participant's success rate was calculated as the number of successfully reached and held target poses divided by the total number of target poses. In the case of a successful trial, the task completion time was calculated. Furthermore, both metrics are again provided for *half-intensity tasks* and *full-intensity tasks* separately (see II-D.4). For further use, the metrics from single-task trials are aggregated as a mean on a TAC level per participant. Missing values due to early termination (see II-D.4) were filled with the success rate of the last synergy minus the tasks corresponding to the new synergy. This approach assumes that the participant would have successfully achieved the same number of synergies again but would not have been able to control the subsequent synergy. The workload, assessed by the NASA-TLX part 1, was evaluated as a mean of the single categories [24] Due to a data loss during the acquisition of the participant, S5 was excluded from the study.

III. RESULTS

A. Objective Measurements

Figure 2 shows the success rate during the TAC tests for the increasing number of synergies across all targets. Missing values (see II-D.5) were anticipated for S2(7), S7(6,7), S8(7), S9(7). A downward trend of the success rate with an increasing number of synergies is visible, except for S3. It is also visible that all participants performed equally or better in TAC 4 than in TAC 3. The success rates of target poses with *half-* and *full-intensity* clearly show that the *full-intensity* poses were performed much better in comparison to the *half-intensity* targets. Furthermore, while the *half-intensity* targets commonly decrease for all participants except for S3, the *full-intensity* targets heavily differ between participants. There, it is particularly noteworthy that three of the participants achieved test results of 100% for $r = 5$ and two reached $\geq 80\%$. For $r = 6$ still, one participant reached 100% success, and three other subjects reached scores $\geq 80\%$.

TABLE I
TASK COMPLETION TIME OF SUCCESSFUL TASKS PER NUMBER OF SYNERGIES r IN [S] (MEAN AND STANDARD DEVIATION)

r	Target intensity		
	<i>all</i>	<i>full</i>	<i>half</i>
3	6.70 ± 1.62	5.96 ± 2.07	7.36 ± 2.34
4	6.14 ± 0.69	5.72 ± 0.93	7.53 ± 1.34
5	6.69 ± 1.70	6.21 ± 1.42	10.95 ± 4.66
6	7.44 ± 2.64	6.85 ± 2.61	10.96 ± 4.28
7	6.79 ± 1.24	6.58 ± 1.32	7.66 ± 1.50

Also, the time to task completion of successful tasks shown in Tab. I shows substantially longer task completion times for *half-* compared to *full-intensity targets* across all

Fig. 2. TAC test performance. Left: Mean success rate (black) and each participant’s success rate across the number of synergies r and targets (*all targets*, *only half-intensity targets*, and *only full-intensity targets*). Right: Box plot shows the success rates across target categories with median and IQR across all participants. Absent values for $S2(7)$, $S7(6,7)$, $S8(7)$, $S9(7)$ were filled as described in II-D.5

synergies. An overall increasing trend in completion time is visible from $r = 3$ to $r = 6$.

B. Subjective Measurement

The results of the NASA-TLX are shown in Fig. 3. Of all TLX dimensions combined, $r = 6$ received the highest scores and thus the highest perceived workload. Amongst the individual dimensions, Temporal Demand (TD) and Frustration (F) received, with the exception of 7 synergies (only $n = 4$), the lowest scores. Mental demand (MD), Effort (E), and Performance (P) were scored higher across most synergies. Physical Demand (PD) stayed relatively consistent across synergies.

IV. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A. Objective Measurements:

The main goal of this work was to improve current state-of-the-art results on incremental unsupervised online myocontrol by leveraging higher-density electrode setups as previously used. In comparison, Gigli et al. achieved success rates of 80% with a maximum of 4 separately controllable synergies [20]. We were able to reach similar success rates with 5-6 independently controllable synergies as shown in Figure 2. At four synergies, near-perfect *full-intensity* target scores were reached in all but one participant. Multiple participants even reached rates of ~80% with seven controllable synergies ($S1$, $S3$, $S4$, $S9$). The significantly lower success rates at 3 active synergies compared to 4, 5, 6, and 7 synergies suggest a strong need for familiarisation and customization of the participants with the protocol and the interaction with the prediction model. The decrease in success rate in *full-intensity* target control at 5, 6, and 7 synergies can be attributed to the increased model complexity and the model’s difficulty in identifying and separating new muscle synergies that were independent of the existing ones.

Prominently, the high success rates in full-intensity target control could not be replicated in *half-intensity* target control, where success rates of less than 50% were achieved even at 3 and 4 synergies by all participants. One potential explanation for this might have been a too strong regularization of the activation coefficients by the ISNMF, or issues in the scaling of the coefficients. A hyperparameter optimization optimized towards the TAC test’s demands could have also improved proportional control. A further possibility is that, in order to activate a myofunction with a half-intensity, the EMG amplitude must be maintained within a specific amplitude range. Conversely, for a full activation, the EMG amplitude merely needs to reach a certain threshold value. Notably, in two participants ($S6$, $S7$), significant model degradation was observed between the model training phase and the TAC tests in higher synergies numbers, suggesting a shift in electrode placement during the completion of the NASA-TLX questionnaire.

Given the much higher number of electrodes used in this study compared to previous work and the high number of controllable synergies in multiple participants, we hypothesize a high possible number of reliably and independently controllable synergies given further optimized hyperparameters and experimental protocol, including longer familiarization with the prediction model and setup, and increased duration of model training before the TAC tests.

B. Subjective Measurements

Similar to Gigli et al. [20], the results of the NASA-TLX scores presented in Figure 3 suggest no consistent decrease or increase of physical demand, mental demand, or frustration with increasing number of synergies despite decreasing success rates towards higher synergy numbers. This suggests that the higher familiarity with the system might be counteracted by the increased difficulty of controlling more myocontrol actions.

Fig. 3. Results of the NASA-TLX questionnaire. Left: NASA-TLX score for the number of synergies. Right: Each questionnaire subcategory result averaged across participants for synergies 4 to 7 with circular ticks from 0 to 0.8, with 0.8 corresponding to a high perceived workload. Subcategories: Temporal Demand (TD), Physical Demand (PD), Mental demand (MD), Frustration (F) Effort (E), and Performance (P). Only the number of participants n who successfully performed the previous synergy TAC test completed the respective NASA-TLX questionnaire.

C. Limitations

All participants in this study were non-disabled individuals. Furthermore, the wrist, hand, and fingers were not constrained with an orthosis. Both factors limit the generalizability to individuals with LD. Since it has been shown that limiting non-disabled subjects to isometric muscle contractions makes them more comparable with individuals with LD [25]. In Addition, this study was conducted in a controlled laboratory setting, which may not fully replicate the complexities and variabilities of daily life scenarios. Furthermore, the TAC-tests did not include simultaneous actions, therefore not evaluating combined control. The gradual increase in controllable Myocontrol functions influenced the results due to familiarisation. However, future users will also start with limited functions and increase the complexity over time. The sequential method therefore models the real use cases.

D. Outlook

Increasing the number of sEMG channels and, therefore, input dimensions not only increases the information density and possibly achievable prediction accuracy but also increases computational demand and model complexity, especially when dealing with the processing of raw EMG signals at high sampling frequencies.

We show that an unsupervised NMF-based control system, such as the one used in this work, can extract a considerable number of muscle synergies from higher-density dry electrode grids. Such a control system could also be used to extract movement intents in an unsupervised fashion from motor unit activation patterns. Motor unit activity extraction was recently shown to be possible in real-time scenarios [26]–[28]. Research suggests, that specific motor

unit recruitment patterns encode distinct DoFs that could pose as lightweight but reliable input signals to the NMF model [29]–[31].

The optimal values for the hyperparameters β and γ , which are used to regulate W and H , directly affect myocontrol quality and vary between individuals. Standardized methods to determine the best hyper-parameters for proportional control for each individual are essential to ensure optimal user satisfaction.

The ISNMF algorithm has the capability to counteract model degradation from sEMG non-stationarities, such as user adaptation, without requiring stored training data or calibration procedures [18]. Moreover, it enables closed-loop co-adaptive learning, thereby enhancing its usability for individuals with congenital LD [32]. Additionally, the progressive and incremental NMF proposed by Gigli et al., allows an increase in the number of extracted synergies, thus enabling the integration of newly learned motor skills [20]. This study confirmed that muscle synergies extracted by ISNMF have the potential to control multiple myocontrol actions (which can be mapped to DOFs) without labeling and calibration procedures. Therefore, it could be used as a myocontrol algorithm for upper limb prosthesis control for individuals with a LD, especially a congenital LD. Furthermore, it allows the identification of distinct muscle synergies with minimal supervision, making it a suitable method for periprosthetic training.

E. Conclusion

This study investigated the feasibility of transferring unsupervised incremental myocontrol to HD-EMG. While preliminary studies based on sEMG and unsupervised incremental

learning demonstrated control over four actions, we showed that it is possible to archive more controllable actions by increasing the number of electrodes.

Nevertheless, the study has certain limitations. It was conducted in a controlled environment and was tested with non-disabled participants. These factors may affect the generalizability of the results for individuals with LDs. Future research should aim to validate these findings with a representative target group and increase the number and density of electrodes even further.

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Giele, C. Giele, C. Bower, and M. Allison, "The incidence and epidemiology of congenital upper limb anomalies: A total population study," *The Journal of Hand Surgery*, vol. 26, no. 4, pp. 628–634, Jul. 2001.
- [2] F. Cordella, A. L. Ciancio, R. Sacchetti, A. Davalli, A. G. Cutti, E. Guglielmelli, and L. Zollo, "Literature Review on Needs of Upper Limb Prosthesis Users," *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, vol. 10, May 2016.
- [3] K. Ziegler-Graham, E. J. MacKenzie, P. L. Ephraim, T. G. Trivison, and R. Brookmeyer, "Estimating the Prevalence of Limb Loss in the United States: 2005 to 2050," *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, vol. 89, no. 3, pp. 422–429, Mar. 2008.
- [4] S.-H. Jo, S.-H. Kang, W.-S. Seo, B.-H. Koo, H.-G. Kim, and S.-H. Yun, "Psychiatric understanding and treatment of patients with amputations," *Yeungnam University Journal of Medicine*, vol. 38, no. 3, pp. 194–201, Jul. 2021.
- [5] S. Salminger, H. Stino, L. H. Pichler, C. Gstoettner, A. Sturma, J. A. Mayer, M. Szivak, and O. C. Aszmann, "Current rates of prosthetic usage in upper-limb amputees – have innovations had an impact on device acceptance?" *Disability and Rehabilitation*, vol. 44, no. 14, pp. 3708–3713, Jul. 2022.
- [6] P. Capi-Morales, C. Piazza, L. Sjoberg, M. G. Catalano, G. Grioli, A. Bicchi, and L. M. Hermansson, "Functional assessment of current upper limb prostheses: An integrated clinical and technological perspective," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 18, no. 8, p. e0289978, Aug. 2023.
- [7] A. Marinelli, N. Boccardo, F. Tessari, D. Di Domenico, G. Caserta, M. Canepa, G. Gini, G. Barresi, M. Laffranchi, L. De Michieli, and M. Semprini, "Active upper limb prostheses: a review on current state and upcoming breakthroughs," *Progress in Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 012001, Jan. 2023.
- [8] A. Phinyomark and E. Scheme, "EMG pattern recognition in the era of big data and deep learning," *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, vol. 2, no. 3, p. 21, Aug. 2018.
- [9] I. Kyranou, S. Vijayakumar, and M. S. Erden, "Causes of Performance Degradation in Non-invasive Electromyographic Pattern Recognition in Upper Limb Prostheses," *Frontiers in Neurobotics*, vol. 12, Sep. 2018.
- [10] A. Gijsberts, R. Bohra, D. Sierra González, A. Werner, M. Nowak, B. Caputo, M. Roa, and C. Castellini, "Stable myoelectric control of a hand prosthesis using non-linear incremental learning," *Frontiers in Neurobotics*, vol. 8, 2014.
- [11] F. Egle, D. Di Domenico, A. Marinelli, N. Boccardo, M. Canepa, M. Laffranchi, L. De Michieli, and C. Castellini, "Preliminary Assessment of Two Simultaneous and Proportional Myocontrol Methods for 3-DoFs Prostheses Using Incremental Learning," in *2023 International Conference on Rehabilitation Robotics (ICORR)*. Singapore, Singapore: IEEE, Sep. 2023. doi: 10.1109/ICORR58425.2023.10304813
- [12] D. Di Domenico, N. Boccardo, A. Marinelli, M. Canepa, E. Gruppioni, M. Laffranchi, and R. Camoriano, "Long-Term Upper-Limb Prosthesis Myocontrol via High-Density sEMG and Incremental Learning," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, 2023.
- [13] A. Hagengruber, U. Leipscher, B. M. Eskofier, and J. Vogel, "A New Labeling Approach for Proportional Electromyographic Control," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 4, p. 1368, Jan. 2022.
- [14] R. C. Simpetru, D. I. Braun, A. U. Simon, M. März, V. Cnejevici, D. S. d. Oliveira, N. Weber, J. Walter, J. Franke, D. Höglinger, C. Prahm, M. Ponfick, and A. D. Vecchio, "MyoGestic: EMG Interfacing Framework for Decoding Multiple Spared Degrees of Freedom of the Hand in Individuals with Neural Lesions," 2023.
- [15] C. Widehammar, K. Lidström Holmqvist, and L. Hermansson, "Training for users of myoelectric multigrip hand prostheses: a scoping review," *Prosthetics and Orthotics International*, vol. 45, no. 5, p. 393, Oct. 2021.
- [16] Ning Jiang, K. Englehart, and P. Parker, "Extracting Simultaneous and Proportional Neural Control Information for Multiple-DOF Prostheses From the Surface Electromyographic Signal," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 56, no. 4, pp. 1070–1080, Apr. 2009.
- [17] C. Lin, B. Wang, N. Jiang, and D. Farina, "Robust extraction of basis functions for simultaneous and proportional myoelectric control via sparse non-negative matrix factorization," *Journal of Neural Engineering*, vol. 15, no. 2, p. 026017, Apr. 2018.
- [18] D. Yeung, I. M. Guerra, I. Barner-Rasmussen, E. Siponen, D. Farina, and I. Vujaklija, "Co-Adaptive Control of Bionic Limbs via Unsupervised Adaptation of Muscle Synergies," *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, vol. 69, no. 8, pp. 2581–2592, Aug. 2022.
- [19] A. Gigli, A. Gijsberts, and C. Castellini, "Unsupervised Myocontrol of a Virtual Hand Based on a Coadaptive Abstract Motor Mapping," in *2022 International Conference on Rehabilitation Robotics (ICORR)*. Rotterdam, Netherlands: IEEE, Jul. 2022. doi: 10.1109/ICORR55369.2022.9896414
- [20] A. Gigli, A. Gijsberts, M. Nowak, I. Vujaklija, and C. Castellini, "Progressive unsupervised control of myoelectric upper limbs," *Journal of Neural Engineering*, vol. 20, no. 6, p. 066016, Nov. 2023.
- [21] F. I. Serdana, S. Muceli, and D. Farina, "Using High Density EMG to Proportionally Control 3D Model of Human Hand," *International Journal on Advanced Science, Engineering and Information Technology*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1118–1126, Jun. 2023.
- [22] M. Barsotti, S. Dupan, I. Vujaklija, S. Došen, A. Frisoli, and D. Farina, "Online Finger Control Using High-Density EMG and Minimal Training Data for Robotic Applications," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 217–223, Apr. 2019.
- [23] R. C. Simpetru, M. März, and A. Del Vecchio, "Proportional and Simultaneous Real-Time Control of the Full Human Hand From High-Density Electromyography," *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, vol. 31, pp. 3118–3131, 2023.
- [24] S. G. Hart and L. E. Staveland, "Development of NASA-TLX (Task Load Index): Results of Empirical and Theoretical Research," in *Advances in Psychology*, ser. Human Mental Workload, P. A. Hancock and N. Meshkati, Eds. North-Holland, Jan. 1988, vol. 52.
- [25] M. B. Kristoffersen, A. W. Franzke, C. K. van der Sluis, R. M. Bongers, and A. Murgia, "Should Hands Be Restricted When Measuring Able-Bodied Participants to Evaluate Machine Learning Controlled Prosthetic Hands?" *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, vol. 28, no. 9, pp. 1977–1983, Sep. 2020.
- [26] J. Rossato, F. Hug, K. Tucker, C. Gibbs, L. Lacourpaille, D. Farina, and S. Avrillon, "I-Spin live: An open-source software based on blind-source separation for real-time decoding of motor unit activity in humans," *eLife*, vol. 12, Sep. 2024.
- [27] D. Y. Barsakcioglu and D. Farina, "A real-time surface EMG decomposition system for non-invasive human-machine interfaces," in *2018 IEEE Biomedical Circuits and Systems Conference (BioCAS)*, Oct. 2018. doi: 10.1109/BIOCAS.2018.8584659
- [28] Y. Wen, S. Avrillon, J. C. Hernandez-Pavon, S. J. Kim, F. Hug, and J. L. Pons, "A convolutional neural network to identify motor units from high-density surface electromyography signals in real time," *Journal of Neural Engineering*, vol. 18, no. 5, p. 056003, Apr. 2021.
- [29] A. Grison, J. I. Pereda, S. Muceli, A. Kundu, F. Baracat, G. Indiveri, E. Donati, and D. Farina, "Intramuscular High-Density Micro-Electrode Arrays Enable High-Precision Decoding and Mapping of Spinal Motor Neurons to Reveal Hand Control," 2023.
- [30] S. Tanzarella, S. Muceli, M. Santello, and D. Farina, "Synergistic Organization of Neural Inputs from Spinal Motor Neurons to Extrinsic and Intrinsic Hand Muscles," *The Journal of Neuroscience*, vol. 41, no. 32, pp. 6878–6891, Aug. 2021.
- [31] M. Obwald, A. L. Cakici, D. S. d. Oliveira, D. I. Braun, and A. D. Vecchio, "Mechanical Hand Synergies during Dynamic Hand Movements are Mostly Controlled in a Non-Synergistic Way by Spinal Motor Neurons," *bioRxiv*, p. 2023.07.25.550369, Jul. 2023.
- [32] C. Igual, L. A. Pardo, J. Hahne, and J. M. Igual, "Myoelectric Control for Upper Limb Prostheses," *Electronics*, vol. 8, no. 11, p. 1244, Oct. 2019.